

Dichotomy of Newtonian Mechanics and a Wavelength in a Quantum Free Particle Part II

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In special relativity, one has the four vectors (x,t) and (p,E) . In order to determine, x or t , one must make a measurement, i.e. have a ruler and clock interval. This suggests one must always have some finite resolution for x and t based on the measuring device. If one uses photons and bounces them off a classical particle, a photon has a wavelength and so different energy photons yield different resolution x measurements. Thus, not only is there a ruler gradation and clock interval, but these may be different depending on how the measurement is done.

For motion, neither x or t may be constants, but p and E can be. X and t values only hold within error ranges associated with their resolutions, but p and E hold at any x point. Thus, there is no notion of x or t intervals for p and E . This is extended to a bound state for which one has: $pp/2m + V(x) = E_n$ (nonrelativistic). In other words one has a dichotomy, a resolution scheme for x,t and a conservation of energy equation that holds at each x .

We have argued in (1) that a math function which describes periodic intervals with maximum entropy in between gradations is $\exp(i b x)$. Furthermore, $b=p$ if one wishes $\exp(ibx)$ to be a probability because b is a conserved quantity, $\exp(ib_1x)\exp(ib_2x) = \exp(i (b_1+b_2)x)$ and only p is always conserved. In other words, a constant p which holds at all x gives rise to a x resolution of \hbar/p . Thus, there is a dichotomy present namely spatial resolution together with the notion of energy or $prms$ which holds at any x irrespective of spatial resolution.

The above leads to a problem if \hbar/p is greater than dx , the distance which would classically be considered to be very small i.e almost a point. Classically this problem does not occur because $\hbar/prms$ is in fact very small compared to classical lengths, but for small lengths the issue does arise. In such a case, one can only have the concept of an average energy at each x together with $prms$ at each x , but a resolution pattern which is not governed by $prms$. In other words, $prms$ does not seem to be an observable, but rather a math construct until $\hbar/prms$ becomes the size of dx .

In other words, in quantum mechanics, the time-independent Schrodinger equation represents average conservation of energy at each x point. This suggests that $KE_{ave}(x)$ is also only an average and that one may actually measure various p values without knowing their exact positions. These p values may actually lie outside the range of $prms$ which is governed by its values between classical turning points. This we argue is linked with interference which means that positive values of $\cos(p_1x)$ at x_1 may combine with a negative value of $\cos(p_2x)$ at x_1 . This only happens, however, for lower energy levels because for very high levels. $\hbar/prms$ is small and it actually becomes a physical value with no need for interference.

A Difference in Measuring x,t and p,E

(x,t) and (p,E) define 4-vectors in special relativity, but the way they are measured seems to be very different. X and t require a ruler gradation and time interval. In other words, there cannot be an infinite x or t resolution. When measuring x with different photons classically, different energy photons have different wavelengths so yield measurements with different error bars, but there are always error bars. Furthermore, for motion x and t require gradations but p and E may be

constants. Thus, one may say that one has a given p and E at each x and t point irrespective of any ruler gradation or clock interval. One may measure p by its impulse on a target at some place.

This, we argue, gives rise to a dichotomy which is not present in Newtonian mechanics, but is in quantum mechanics. Energy conservation holds at each x point, but there must be an expression from x gradations with maximum entropy in between the gradations.

In (1), we suggested that a math function which described periodic gradation with maximum entropy between gradations is:

$$\exp(i b x) \quad ((1))$$

Here one moves smoothly along a circle, i.e. maximum entropy, but each revolution represents adding a new gradation. It is only the projections $\cos(bx)$ and $\sin(bx)$ which show positive and negative values and not smoothness.

By noting that b is a conserved quantity through: $\exp(ib_1x)\exp(ib_2x) = \exp(i(b_1+b_2)x)$, one may suggest that $b=p$, because momentum is always conserved. This means that \hbar/p defines a gradation interval in space, but at the same time p and $pp/2m$ have the same value at each x point.

This, we argue, leads to interesting consequences for a bound state.

Bound State

A bound state has energy conservation: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$ with $KE_{ave}(x) = \frac{p_{rms}(x)^2}{2m}$.

This equation holds at each x point. A problem arises if \hbar/p_{rms} is greater than what would be considered a tiny dx classically. Fortunately this does not happen numerically classically, but it may happen for smaller lengths. In such a case, $p_{rms}(x)$ which is supposed to hold at a point is associated with a resolution of \hbar/p_{rms} which is a contradiction. Thus, one may suggest that in such a case, $p_{rms}(x)$ does not represent physical motion, but rather an average. In other words, one must deal with specific p values and $\exp(ipx)$ s. These, may combine as probabilities, i.e. Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to create a resolution pattern, but one must have $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$ for each x , even though $KE_{ave}(x)$ is a math average and one may actually measure p values which are greater than any $p_{rms}(x)$ value within the classical turning point for quantum low energy states.

We note that when $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$ is not the size of dx , then one not only has $\exp(ipx)$ s which sum, but interference which means that a positive value of a projection of $\exp(ipx)$, namely $\cos(p_1x)$ at x_1 may combine with a negative value of $\cos(p_2x)$ at x_1 . This plus minus combination follows from projections of $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that the notion of conservation of average energy must hold because one uses $V(x)$ which is based on this idea. This conservation statement then leads to the values of $a(p)$ in Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Consider:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \frac{\sum p a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx)}{\sum p a(p) \exp(ipx)} \quad ((3))$$

If one uses $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} + V(x) W = E_n W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((4))

then one has a kind of energy equation for each $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, for each $\exp(ipx)$ which creates a resolution of \hbar/p , the energy at each x point is:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E_n a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Various p values of ((5)) may then be added to obtain ((4)).

We suggest that if \hbar/p_{rms} is of the order of dx , then there is no reason for it to be created by interference of different p values. A single p value equal to $p_{rms}(x)$ is sufficient and ((5)) should then be equivalent to:

$$p_{rms}(x) p_{rms}(x) a(p) \exp(ipx) + V(x) a(p) \exp(ipx) = E_n a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

In other words, interference goes away by itself at high energy and one has conservation of energy within each $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a dichotomy exists because the two 4-vectors (x,t) and (p,E) are associated with very different kinds of measurements. X and t require ruler and clock gradations and these need not be fixed. For example, different energy photons have different wavelengths and lead to different x resolutions, i.e. error bars. A p and E set may be constant and be mapped to all x points irrespective of resolution or error bars. One may measure p by a single impulse hit.

When considering conservation of energy, it holds at each x point irrespective of resolution. At the same time, there should be a spatial resolution. In (1), we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ describes this resolution and that one may use $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability. There is a physical resolution of \hbar/p for a particle moving with p . If $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$ is not the size of dx , then $p_{rms}(x)$ is only a mathematical average. In such a case, one must use interference with $\sum p^2 / 2m a(p) \exp(ipx) / \sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$ to find $KE_{ave}(x)$. Here interference means one must have a positive value of a projection of $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. $\cos(p_1 x)$ at x_1 add to a negative value of $\cos(p_2 x)$ at x_1 .

If on the other hand, $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$ is of the order of dx , then one does not require interference and a $p_{rms}(x)$ may equal a specific $\exp(ipx)$ at x . At the next x point, it is represented by $\exp(ip_2 x)$. In such a way, both resolution and conservation of energy are satisfied.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. A Quantum Free Particle Does Not Seem to Maximize Spatial Entropy Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2024)